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Sorption and Desorption Studies of Crystal Violet and Malachite Green on and from Synthetic Zeolites 3A and AW500

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CRYSTAL violet and malachite green, which are triphenylmethane dyes, were used for interaction with synthetic zeolites 3A and AW500. The interacted samples have been studied by thermogravimetric, photometric and infrared spectroscopic methods. The zeolite 3A was in powder form while the other was in 1/16" cylindrical pellet form. Their characteristics are known from earlier studies¹⁻³.

Experimental

The zeolites were kept in contact with aqueous solutions of the two dyes for several days. They were heated from time to time to effect maximum interaction and later kept inside the refrigerator also for several days. The zeolites were filtered off from the excess liquid and dried in air. The thermogravimetric studies were carried out on a thermobalance supplied by the Fertilizer Corporation of India, Sindri, at a heating rate of 10°/minute between 293 and 1073°K. Absorption data were collected between 200 and 1000 nm by means of a spectrophotometer with reflectance attachment (Model

VSK-2P). The IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer instrument (Model 577) between 4000 and 200 cm⁻¹ in cesium iodide. The elemental analyses were done on a Thomas CH-Analyzer 35 and Coleman N-Analyzer 29. The relevant data have been reproduced in Table 1.

Discussion

The zeolite samples start losing weight around 353°K and process of weight loss continues till 873°K for malachite green-sorbed AW500 and 933°K for the other three samples. Maximum weight loss for dehydration occurs around 430°K and for the desorption of the dyes at about 530°K. Thermogravimetric data were utilised for evaluating the kinetic parameters of the weight loss sequence, on the basis of the relation, $g(\alpha) = [-\log_e(1-\alpha)]^{1/n} = Kt = ze^{-E/RT}$, suggested by Avrami⁴ and Erofejev⁵ where K is the specific reaction rate constant and E is the corresponding activation energy of the isothermal process. Values of α were calculated from

$$\alpha = \frac{(W_t - W_i)}{(W_o - W_i)}$$

where W_t is the indicated weight at time or temperature, t ; W_o is the initial sample weight; and W_i is the residual weight at the end of the process under study. The plots between $g(\alpha)$ and time are non-linear for $n=1, 2$ and 3 . These plots show that the thermal events occur at two different rates. The plots for $\log_e [g(\alpha)/T^2]$ vs $1000/T$ are straight lines having different slopes for dehydration and desorption of sorbed species for $n=1, 2$ and 3 . Both the processes are first order reactions⁶. The extent of dye-sorption is obtained from the photometric data as well as the percentages of carbon in the various samples. It is clear that crystal violet is more extensively sorbed than malachite green and zeolite 3A exhibits greater capacity for dye-sorption compared to AW500. IR spectra of the samples indicate that the sorption occurs by hydrogen bonding atleast in the case of 3A as the absorption bands due to water at about 3500 and 1650 cm⁻¹ are broadened considerably due to the presence of the sorbed species. This broadening effect is not pronounced in the case of zeolite AW500.

TABLE 1

Zeolite	Weight Loss %	Carbon %	Hydrogen %	Nitrogen %
Crystal violet sorbed 3A	28.5	4.88	2.76	Negligible
Crystal violet sorbed AW500	18.7	1.70	2.24	"
Malachite green sorbed 3A	23.9	1.34	1.84	"
Malachite green sorbed AW500	18.6	Negligible	1.57	"

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Effect of Non-Aqueous Solvents on Depolarising Action of Cadmium (II)-N-[(β -Aminoethyl)]-Ethanolamine Complexes at D.M.E.*

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THE electrochemical studies of cadmium(II)-N-[(β -aminoethyl)]-ethanolamine complexes have been carried out at dropping mercury electrode. Two complexes with metal to ligand ratio as 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 have been reported at pH 6.6 ± 0.1 and temperature 303°K. Stepwise formation constants of cadmium(II)-N-[(β -aminoethyl)]-ethanolamine complexes have been determined in both aqueous and aqueous non-aqueous mixed media. The studies have also been extended to the effect of formamide, dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO), methanol, *n*-propanol and isopropanol on the formation constants of the complexes. The effects of ligand concentration on complexation reaction have been examined in terms of relative distribution of metal and ligand in solution.

The importance of amines and several other nitrogen-containing compounds has been recognised in the biochemical, analytical and pharmaceutical fields. Electroanalytical investigation of various metal ions with nitrogen-containing ligands are thus useful and recently studied by a number of workers¹⁻⁵. However, there is no reference to the pursuit of polarographic studies on the cadmium(II)-N-[(β -aminoethyl)]-ethanolamine complexes, therefore, the present investigation were undertaken.

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Experimental

A manual polarograph with a scalamp galvanometer acting as a current recorder was used in all the investigations. The dropping mercury electrodes had the characteristics $m=1.8$ mg. sec⁻¹ and $t=4.3$ sec. (open circuit). Chemicals used were of reagent grade. The solvents were purified, wherever necessary, by standard methods.

In each system the concentration of Cd(II) was $5 \times 10^{-4}M$. Ionic strength (μ) was 1.0M maintained constant by adding requisite amounts of sodium perchlorate in all the test solutions. The pH was maintained 6.6 ± 0.1 by Toshiniwal pH meter. Purified nitrogen was presaturated with the given aqueous-nonaqueous solvent mixture was passed for thirty minutes to remove dissolved oxygen in each test solution. Temperature was kept constant at 303°K by the help of Haake type ultrathermostat.

Results and Discussion

The reversibility of reduction with involvement of two electrons and with controlled diffusion in aqueous and aquo-nonaqueous mixed media were concluded for cadmium-N-[(β -aminoethyl)] ethanolamine system, from the slopes (31 ± 1) of log plots and proportionality of i_d and \sqrt{h} respectively at 303°K.

To investigate the effect of change of ligand concentration, polarograms of 0.05 mM cadmium(II) mixed with various concentration (0.0 to 0.05M) of N-[(β -aminoethyl)]-ethanolamine were recorded. The shift in half-wave potential to more negative values, alongwith a decrease in diffusion current (i_d) on increasing ligand concentration, indicated the formation of complexes in each system. The nature of wave did not change at higher concentrations of ligand.

The values of overall formation constants, evaluated by DeFord-Hume's method⁶ are comprehended below :

Overall formation Constants of Cd(II)-N-[(β -aminoethyl)]-ethanolamine Complexes by DeFord-Hume's Method.

Solvent Media	log β_1	log β_2
Pure aqueous	7.14	9.36
40% Methanol + Aqueous	8.54	9.07
60% Methanol + Aqueous	9.11	9.54
25% DMSO + Aqueous	8.74	10.00
40% DMSO + Aqueous	9.47	11.13
40% Isopropanol + Aqueous	6.84	7.80
60% Isopropanol + Aqueous	6.92	8.14
25% N-Propanol + Aqueous	7.00	7.81
40% N-Propanol + Aqueous	6.89	7.63
25% Formamide + Aqueous	6.25	7.69
40% Formamide + Aqueous	6.90	7.20
60% Formamide + Aqueous	6.84	7.11